

BioExcel-2 Project Number 823830

D4.3 – Progress report and update on training and dissemination plan

WP4: Dissemination and training

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Executive Summary

This document describes the dissemination activities that have been completed since June 2019 and the training activities completed since January 2020. It provides an estimate of the impact that has been achieved by these activities. The dissemination section presents information about the project website, social media channels, dissemination events and publications. We also present the future strategy for dissemination and updated plans for training activities in the second half of the project.

Both dissemination and training activities have adapted to the pandemic situation the world faces at present. The rapid response from the BioExcel Centre of Excellence to disseminate their work on COVID-19 research and to convert the BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular simulations into a virtual event resulted in an extremely positive response from the community. The tweet advertising our blog on BioExcel's work on COVID-19 Research achieved 14,000 impressions, making it our most popular tweet so far, and the Summer School was the most viewed page on the website and received a record number of applications: 180.

To highlight BioExcel's work on COVID-19 research, a dedicated page has been created on our website. The newsletter has been revamped with a new banner and social media platforms have shown significant growth. In 2019, there have been 49 dissemination events and 46 publications. Since January 2020, there have been 13 dissemination and training events and 18 publications.

We describe an overview of the training events completed in the first half of 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic has had an effect on face-to-face events, but this effect has been limited thanks to the experience that we already had in running remote courses. After the success of our pilot courses in 2019, we added remote courses as part of the BioExcel training programme. We have run 6 courses and used the experience gained to convert the BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations 2020 into an online event. For each course, we present the contents and setup, and discuss the feedback received through post-course surveys. Most respondents gave one of the two top ratings in a question regarding an overall rating of the course. BioExcel will continue to deliver training to the biomolecular research community through already planned events listed here and others yet to be confirmed.

The last additions to the competency mapper tool move it into the area of career development. It enables us to create reference profiles reflecting different roles in the BioExcel community and rated against the BioExcel competency framework. Users can create their own profiles and compare competencies between two different profiles.

The long-term impact of previous training activities is also described here. It shows that most respondents use the skills gained during the courses and many of them teach others, which broadens the impact that our training has in the community.

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1. Introduction

This document follows the previous deliverables, D4.1 and D4.2, where the plans for dissemination and training for the BioExcel CoE were presented. It describes the dissemination and training activities carried out since the date of the previous corresponding deliverable. The dissemination activities included are, therefore, since May 2019; and the training activities since January 2020.

The dissemination section includes the strategies implemented through the channels used by the CoE (website, newsletter, social media) and lists of events and publications with participation from the BioExcel CoE. The training section includes a description of the events organised by BioExcel and the last developments in the competency mapper tool. Both sections explain the impact of the activities carried out so far and the plans for the rest of the project.

Since the beginning of 2020, the world is facing a pandemic of COVID-19 that has affected our lives, including BioExcel activities, adding a new research focus, moving events into an online environment or postponing others. This is reflected below, where we describe how both the dissemination and training activities have adapted to this new situation.

2. Dissemination

Here we present an update on the dissemination strategies implemented since May 2019 using our digital marketing channels and the respective impact of each strategy.

2.1 Dissemination during COVID-19

Since the onset of the COVID-19 crisis, BioExcel partners have launched a series of actions to support research into SARS-CoV-2. To highlight BioExcel's work in this space and share resources with the wider community, a dedicated page titled '[COVID-19 Research](#)' (Fig. 1) has been created on the BioExcel website to showcase research articles, web server interfaces and international collaborations with organisations such as Molecular Sciences Software Institute ([MolSSI](#)).

This research is also being communicated via newsletters and social media, with the blog titled '[BioExcel Centre of Excellence in support of COVID-19 Research](#)' viewed 14,000 times on Twitter making it the most viewed tweet on our channel so far.

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Figure 1. COVID-19 Research section on the BioExcel website

2.2 Website

The BioExcel website acts as another main channel of dissemination. Through the use of SEO (Search engine optimization) friendly blog posts and event posting, the website is able to capture new audiences as well as acting as an archive of existing news and events. In addition, the website acts as a central hub, directing visitors to BioExcel's other social media presences and facilitating the registration of the newsletter. A live feed of the BioExcel Twitter account can also be seen, keeping the front page of the website up to date.

2.2.1 Visitors

Figure 2. Google analytics with user information

Since May 2019, BioExcel has received over 22,500 unique visitors, with over 4,400 of these being returning visitors (Fig. 2). The website has seen visitors from 144 different countries, with the major visiting countries being the United States, United Kingdom, India, Germany and Italy. (Fig. 3)

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Figure 3. Google analytics with demographics

Acquisition analytics identify that the major source of traffic derives from organic web searches. This is followed by direct visits and social media referrals, of which the main being BioExcel's Twitter channel. (Fig.4)

	Users ↓	New Users ↓	Sessions ↓
	22,656	22,554	35,264
1 ■ Organic Search	11,463	<div style="width: 50%;"></div>	
2 ■ Direct	6,849	<div style="width: 30%;"></div>	
3 ■ Referral	2,964	<div style="width: 15%;"></div>	
4 ■ Social	2,490	<div style="width: 10%;"></div>	
5 ■ Email	417	<div style="width: 2%;"></div>	

Figure 4. Google analytics with acquisition traffic

2.2.2 Site Content

<input type="checkbox"/>	Page ?	Pageviews ? ↓	Unique Pageviews ?
		63,827 % of Total: 100.00% (63,827)	54,392 % of Total: 100.00% (54,392)
<input type="checkbox"/>	1. /	11,651 (18.25%)	9,696 (17.83%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	2. /events/bioexcel-summer-school-on-biomolecular-simulations-2020/	4,688 (7.34%)	3,928 (7.22%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	3. /events/bioexcel-summer-school-on-biomolecular-simulations-2019/	1,771 (2.77%)	1,516 (2.79%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	4. /software/gromacs/	1,346 (2.11%)	1,174 (2.16%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	5. /category/webinar/	1,287 (2.02%)	962 (1.77%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	6. /services/training/summerschool2019/	1,126 (1.76%)	989 (1.82%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	7. /software/cpmd/	1,122 (1.76%)	926 (1.70%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	8. /webinar-clustering-free-energy-landscapes-from-molecular-dynamics-simulations-2020-05-12/	1,115 (1.75%)	978 (1.80%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	9. /news-and-events/events/	1,081 (1.69%)	884 (1.63%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	10. /events/bioexcel-prace-seasonal-school-2019-sweden-hpc-for-life-sciences/	940 (1.47%)	790 (1.45%)

Figure 5. Google analytics with most viewed pages

The most viewed content on the website was clearly the summer school events with "Remote BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations" receiving 3 times more views than the second most viewed page. This is then followed by software and webinar related content (Fig.5).

2.3 Newsletters

Newsletters continue to play an integral part of digital marketing. Since the start of January 2020, the newsletter template has been revamped with an updated banner and targeted content (Fig. 6).

In addition, to increase our efforts to target the industry audience, a separate section has been created to include a minimum of one industry-based news item in the monthly newsletter (see D3.4 - User Community Support and Engagement Report, half-time update, for additional information).

Analytics show that with an average open rate of 31.3% and click rate 8.45%, we are exceeding industry standards (As per campaign monitor's [resource article](#); 15-25% open rate and 2.5% click-through rate).

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Display problems? [Open this email in your web browser.](#)

Dear Michelle,

As the COVID-19 global health emergency continues to impact our lives, BioExcel partners are working on several international initiatives to bring together advanced software and supercomputing centers. Also, in collaboration with Molecular Sciences Software Institute we have launched a [community data repository](#) for COVID-19 related simulation data.

BioExcel is offering expert support to academic and industrial researchers working on modelling and simulations of systems related to SARS-CoV-2. If you are interested, please get in touch with us at info@bioexcel.eu.

Lastly, don't forget to check out our upcoming webinars in May!

Michelle Mendonca
Dissemination Officer

Figure 6. Updated newsletter banner

2.4 Social Media Channels

2.4.1 Twitter - The BioExcel twitter channel has shown an upward growth with a total of 1858 followers and 60.4 K impressions (as of 27 May 2020). An example of a successful tweet is shown below, which gained 14K impressions. (Fig. 7)

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Figure 7. Top tweet for April 2020

2.4.2 LinkedIn - The LinkedIn channel has seen an upward growth gaining 484 followers (as of 27 May 2020). A successful example of a post with 1,724 impressions is shown below (Fig. 8).

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Figure 8. Top performing LinkedIn post

2.5 Dissemination and training events

2.5.1 EMBO Workshop: Advances and Challenges in Biomolecular Simulations, Brno, Czech Republic

The [EMBO workshop: Advances and Challenges in Biomolecular Simulations](#) sponsored by BioExcel was due to take place 18-21 October 2020 in Brno, Czech Republic. The aim of the conference is to bring together top researchers in the fields of biomolecular simulations, integrative modelling, free energy and drug design, workflows and automation and data integration. Through this conference, we intend to provide a platform for knowledge exchange for the community on a wider scale. An extensive communication strategy was planned with a 'Save the Date' campaign seen below (Fig. 9), followed by the 'Registration open' announcement which was sent out on various channels and generated a positive response from the community.

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Figure 9. 'Save the date' banner created as part of the communication plan

However, due to the current coronavirus pandemic, the organising committee has decided to postpone the conference to 17 - 20 October 2021 in the interest of the safety of attendees. Marketing activities will resume after August 2020 as we review the registration and abstract submission deadlines.

2.5.2 Events and Publications

The following training and dissemination events shown in Table 1 (2019) and Table 2 (2020) were carried out by BioExcel members from January 2019 to May 2020.

No	Date	Event name	Location	Participant Number
1	February 4-6, 2019	Multiscale Modeling from Macromolecules to Cell: Opportunities and Challenges of Biomolecular Simulations	Lausanne, Switzerland	45
2	February 21, 2019	FocusCoE kick-off	Frankfurt, Germany	N/A
3	February 25 - 26, 2019	Talks by Dr Paul Bauer at University of Oxford	Oxford, UK	30
4	February 25 March 1, 2019	SIAM conference on Computational Science and Engineering	Spokane, USA	1000
5	March 1, 2019	Talk by Dr. Alexandre Bonvin at the workshop on "Working Towards Federating Structural Models and Data"	Baltimore, USA	60
6	March 6, 2019	Talk by Dr. Alexandre Bonvin at the Biophysical Society meeting workshop on "Methods for Integrative Structure Modeling of Biomolecular Systems"	Baltimore, USA	200
7	March 28, 2019	Talk by Dr. Alexandre Bonvin at the CompBioMed workshop on containerisation	Amsterdam, NL	30
8	April 3-5, 2019	7th CAPRI evaluation meeting 2019	Hinxton, UK	86
9	April 3-5, 2019	6th European Chemical Biology Symposium	Madrid, Spain	200

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10	April 9-11, 2019	60 ans du Laboratoire de Biochimie Théorique	Paris, France	65
11	April 10-12, 2019	EOSC-hub week 2019	Prague, Czech Republic	240
12	April 24, 2019	PDC-SeRC lunchtime seminar series	Stockholm, SE	15
13	May 06 - 07 2019	LifeTime Opening Conference	Berlin, Germany	-
14	May 6-8, 2019	EGI Conference 2019	Amsterdam, Netherlands	200
15	May 13-17, 2019	Challenges in large scale biomolecular simulation 2019: Bridging theory and Experiments	Cargese, France	44
16	May 13-17, 2019	EuroHPC Summit Week 2019	Poznan, Poland	-
17	May 14, 2019	Towards the atomistic-resolution of chromosomes	Pisa, Italy	50
18	May 14-17, 2019	Education and Training summit	Cape town, South Africa	-
19	17 May, 2019	BioExcel Webinar #35 GROMACS 2019 - overview of the new features and capabilities	Online	53
20	May 19-24, 2019	12th European Workshop in Drug Design	Certosa di Pontignano, Siena, Italy	-
21	May 27-28, 2019	BioExcel Alchemical Free Energy Workshop 2019	Göttingen, Germany	115
22	May 28-29, 2019	PRACE IP6 WP8 project kickoff	Bratislava, Slovakia	200
23	May 29-31, 2019	iNEXT workshop Integrated methodologies and approaches for structural biology	Brno, Czech Republic	150
24	June 9-14, 2019	Gordon Research Conference: Computational Aspects of Biomolecular NMR	Les Diablerets, Switzerland	112
25	June 11-12, 2019	TERATEC 2019 Forum	France	-
26	June 14, 2019	CP2K meeting in UK	London, UK	-
27	June 16-20, 2019	ISC High Performance 2019	Frankfurt, Germany	3500
28	June 17-20, 2019	CECAM workshop on coevolutionary approaches to protein and protein-complexes structure prediction and design	Lausanne, Switzerland	35
29	June 23 - 28, 2019	Synergy of experiment and computation in quantitative systems biology	Nové Hradky, Czech Republic	80
30	June 24 - 28, 2019	Summer School (1st week@Snellius) and workshop (2nd week@Oort) in Multi-Scale Modelling	Leiden, Netherlands	48
31	June 26, 2019	Industrial focus group meeting mostly with SMEs	Barcelona, Spain	6
32	July 12, 2019	FocusCoE for HPC application, WP3 call	Telecon	15
33	July 22-26 2019	Asia Pacific Advanced Network Meeting	Putrajaya, Malaysia	250
34	August 22 – 23, 2019	D3R 2019 Workshop	La Jolla	75
35	August 25 – 30, 2019	17th International Congress on Photobiology	Barcelona, Spain	540
36	August 29 – 30, 2019	Finnish Computational Chemistry Days 2019	Kuopio, Finland	70

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37	September 03 – 05, 2019	CECAM workshop “Frontiers in multi-scale molecular modeling of photo-receptors”	Tel Aviv, Israel	60
38	September 04 – 06, 2019	7th Annual CCPBioSim Conference - Frontiers in Biomolecular Simulation	Bristol, UK	120
39	September 23 – 27, 2019	9th International Symposium on Photochromism	Paris, France	250
40	September 24, 2019	BioExcel Webinar #39 Accelerating sampling in GROMACS with the AWH method	Online	45
41	September 24 – 27, 2019	Research Object workshop at eScience2019	San Diego, US	40
42	October 07-08, 2019	Aviesian symposium	Paris, France	100
43	October 09 - 11, 2019	Advanced GROMACS, HADDOCK + PMX Workshop	Espoo, Finland	22 + 21 remotely
44	November 03 – 05, 2019	MoISSI Workshop: Molecular Dynamics Software Interoperability	Brooklyn, New York	
45	November 17-22, 2019	Supercomputing 2019	Denver, US	11000
46	November 28 – 29, 2019	Advances in Computational Biology Conference 2019	Barcelona, Spain	
47	December 2, 2019	Mini-symposium: From coarse-grained to atomistic description of biophysical processes	Stockholm, Sweden	40
48	December 5, 2019	BioExcel Webinar #41 A walk through simulation parameter options (.mdp files) for GROMACS	Online	96
49	December 10-11, 2019	BioFIT	France	1300

Table 1. 2019 Dissemination Events

No	Date	Event name	Location	Participant Number
1	January 31, 2020	Using Twitter to promote your project	Online	10
2	February 20, 2020	BioExcel Webinar #42 What’s new in GROMACS 2020	Online	43
3	February 24-28, 2020	ResOps: Cloud-native tools and technology for researchers	Online	27
4	March 11-12, 2020	Introduction to Simulation Environments for Life Sciences	Barcelona, Spain	11
5	April 2, 2020	HADDOCK/COVID activities presentation at WLCG operation meeting	Online	53
6	April 3, 2020	Using Twitter to promote your project	Online	12
7	April 21, 2020	CECAM Webinars: CoVid-19: challenges and responses in simulation, modeling and beyond, THE PROTEINS OF SARS-COV-2, JOINT DATA REPOSITORIES, AND COMMUNITY COLLABORATIONS	Online	1,947 views (Accessed 15 May)
8	April 24, 2020	EGI webinar: WeNMR - Structural biology in the cloud - 10 years of experience of using EGI services	Online	15

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9	April 28, 2020	BioExcel Webinar #43 Density guided simulations - combining cryo-EM data and molecular dynamics simulation	Online	89
10	May 05, 2020	CECAM Webinars: CoVid-19: challenges and responses in simulation, modeling and beyond, HPC AND BIG DATA APPROACHES IN COVID-19 RESEARCH	Online	1,307 views (Accessed 15 May)
11	June 09, 2020	Preparing to run biomolecular QM/MM simulations with CP2K using AmberTools	Online	TBC
12	June 11, 2020	BioExcel Webinar #46 The HADDOCK2.4 server - new features and a guided demo	Online	TBC
13	June 22 - 26, 2020	Remote BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations	Online	TBC

Table 2. 2020 Training and Dissemination events, T= Training, D= Dissemination

2.6 Publications

The following publications shown in Table 3 and 4 were published by BioExcel members.

No	Authors	Title	Journal	DOI	Open Access Link
1	A.W.Yee et al.	A molecular mechanism for transthyretin amyloidogenesis	Nature Communications	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-08609-z	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-019-08609-z
2	B. Jiménez-García, K. Elez, P.I. Koukos, A.M.J.J. Bonvin and A. Vangone	PRODIGY-crystal: a web-tool for classification of biological interfaces in protein complexes	Bioinformatics	10.1093/bioinformatics/btz437	https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz437
3	L. Orellana et al.	Oncogenic mutations at the EGFR ectodomain structurally converge to remove a steric hindrance on a kinase-coupled cryptic epitope	PNAS	https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1821442116	https://www.pnas.org/content/116/20/10009
4	Levi N. Naden et al.	MolSSI and BioExcel Workflow Workshop 2018 Report	Arxiv.org: Computer Science->Software Engineering	No DOI yet: https://arxiv.org/abs/1905.11863	https://arxiv.org/abs/1905.11863
5	J. M. Haugaard Olsen et al.	MiMiC: A Novel Framework for Multiscale Modeling in Computational Chemistry	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jctc.9b00093	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.jctc.9b00093
6	News article	A study makes a significant contribution to progress in gene therapy efficiency by identifying			https://www.irbbarcelona.org/en/news/a-study-makes-a-significant-contribution-to-progress-in-gene-

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		the source of asymmetry in RNA · DNA hybrids			therapy-efficiency-by-identifying
7	M. Aldeghi, B.L. de Groot, V. Gapsys	Accurate Calculation of Free Energy Changes upon Amino Acid Mutation	Computational Methods in Protein Evolution	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-8736-8_2	https://link.springer.com/protocol/10.1007/978-1-4939-8736-8_2
8	E. Coci et al	Pyruvate carboxylase deficiency type A and type C: Characterization of five novel pathogenic variants in PC and analysis of the genotype–phenotype correlation	Human mutation	https://doi.org/10.1002/humu.23742	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/humu.23742
9	V. Gapsys and B.L. de Groot	Comment on 'Valid molecular dynamics simulations of human hemoglobin require a surprisingly large box size'	eLife	https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.44718.001	https://cdn.elifesciences.org/articles/44718/elifesciences-44718-v1.pdf
10	A. Vangone, J. Schaarschmidt, P. Koukos, C. Geng, N. Citro, M.E. Trellet, L.C. Xue and A.M.J.J. Bonvin	Large-scale prediction of binding affinity in protein-small ligand complexes: the PRODIGY-LIG web server.	Bioinformatics	https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty816	
11	P.I. Koukos, L.C. Xue and A.M.J.J. Bonvin	Protein-ligand pose and affinity prediction. Lessons from D3R Grand Challenge 3	J. Comp. Aid. Mol. Des.	https://doi.org/10.1007/s10822-018-0148-4	https://doi.org/10.1007/s10822-018-0148-4
12	C. Geng, A. Vangone, G.E. Folkers, L.C. Xue and A.M.J.J. Bonvin	iSEE: Interface structure, evolution, and energy-based machine learning predictor of binding affinity changes upon mutations	Proteins: Struc. Funct. & Bioinformatics	https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.25630	https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.25630
13	C. Geng, Li J. Roel-Touris and A.M.J.J. Bonvin	Finding the $\Delta\Delta G$ spot: Are predictors of binding affinity changes upon mutations in protein-protein interactions ready for it?	WIREs Computational Molecular Science	https://doi.org/10.1002/wcms.1410	https://doi.org/10.1002/wcms.1410
14	C. Geng, Y. Jung, N. Renaud, V. Honavar, A.M.J.J. Bonvin and L.C. Xue	iScore: A novel graph kernel-based function for scoring protein-protein docking models	Bioinformatics	http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz496	http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz496
15	A. Basciu, G. Mallocci, F. Pietrucci, A.M.J.J. Bonvin and A.V. Vargiu.	Holo-like and druggable protein conformations from enhanced-sampling of binding pocket shape.	J. Chem. Inf. and Mod.	http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.8b00730	http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jcim.8b00730
16	L. Goldbach, B. Vermeulen, S. Caner, M. Liu, C. Tysoe, L. van Gijzel, R. Yoshisada, M.E. Trellet, H. van Ingen, G. Brayer, A.M.J.J. Bonvin and S. Jongkees	Folding Then Binding vs. Folding Through Binding in Macrocyclic Peptide Inhibitors of Human Pancreatic alpha-Amylase.	ACS Chemical Biology	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acscchembio.9b00290	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acscchembio.9b00290

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17	P.Dans, D.Gallego, A.Balaceanu, L.Darré, H.Gómez and M.Orozco.	Modeling, simulations and bioinformatics at the service of RNA structure	Chem. (Cell Group)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2451929418304352	
18	A.Kuzmanic, P.D.Dans and M.Orozco	An in-depth look at DNA crystals through the prism of molecular Dynamics simulations	Chem. (Cell Group)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2451929418305709	
19	M.Terrazas, D.Sánchez, F.Battistini, N.Villegasm I.Brun-Heath and M.Orozco	A multifunctional Toolkit for target-directed cancer therapy	Chem.Com m	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30574643/	
20	F.Colizzi, A.Hospital, S.Zivanovic and M.Orozco	Predicting the limit of intramolecular H-bonding with classical molecular Dynamics	Angew.Che m	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/anie.201810922	
21	L.Orellana, A.Gaseley-Thorme, R.Lerma, J.Gustavsson, A.Parisian, A.Hospital, I.Brun-Heath, T-N.Cordeiro, P.Bernadó, A.M.Scot, E.Lindah, W.Cavenee, F.Fumary and M.Orozco.	Oncogenic mutations in the EGFR ectodomain converge structurally to mimic the transition State detected by mAB806	Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6525488/	
22	A.Balaceanu, D.Buitrago, J.Walther, A.Hospital, P.D.Dans and M.Orozco.	Long range effects can modulate helical properties of DNA	Nucleic Acids Res.	https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz255	
23	M.Terrazas, V.Genna, G.Portella, N.Villegas, D.Sanchez, C.Arnán, C.Pulido-Quetglas, R.Johnson, R.Guigó, I.Brun-Heath, A.Aviño, R.Eritja and M.Orozco	The Origins and the Biological Consequences of the Pur/Pyr DNA-RNA Asymmetry	Chem. (Cell Group)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2451929419301603	
24	S.Arangundy-Franklin, A.I.Taylor, B.T.Porebski, V.Gena, S.Peak-Chew, A.Vaisman, R.Woodgate, M.Orozco and P.Holliger.	A synthetic genetic polymer with an uncharged backbone chemistry based on alkyl-phosphonate nucleic acids	Nature Chem	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41557-019-0255-4	
25	A.Escobedo, B.Topal, M.B.Kunze, J.Aranda G.Chiesa, D.Mungianu, G.Bernado-Seisedos, B.Eftekharzadeh, M.Gairi, R.Pierattelli, I.C.Felli, T.Diercks, O.Millet, J.García, M.Orozco, R.Crehuet, K.Lindorff-Larsen and X.Salvatella	Side chain to main chain hydrogen bonds stabilize a polyglutamine helix in a transcription factor	Nature Comm.	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-09923-2	
26	J.Aranda, M.Terrazas, H.Gómez, N.Villegas and M.Orozco.	An artificial DNAzyme RNA ligase shows a reaction mechanism	Nature Catal.	https://www.nature.com/articles/	

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		resembling that of cellular polymerases		s41929-019-0290-y	
27	M. Aldeghi, V. Gapsys, B.L. de Groot	Predicting Kinase Inhibitor Resistance: Physics-Based and Data-Driven Approaches	ACS Central Science	10.1021/acscentsci.9b00590	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acscentsci.9b00590
28	P. Andrio, A. Hospital, J. Conejero, Luis Jordà, M. Del Pino, L. Codó, S. Soiland-Reyes, C. Goble, D. Lezzi, R.M. Badia, M. Orozco, J.L. Gelpí	BioExcel Building Blocks, a software library for interoperable biomolecular simulation workflows	Nature Scientific Data	10.1038/s41597-019-0177-4	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6736963/
29	V. Bolnykh J. M. Haugaard Olsen, S. Meloni, M. P. Bircher, E. Ippoliti, P. Carloni, and Ursula Rothlisberger	Extreme Scalability of DFT-Based QM/MM MD Simulations Using MiMiC	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	10.1021/acs.jctc.9b00424	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/pdf/10.1021/acs.jctc.9b00424
30	Emanuele G Coci, Vytautas Gapsys, Natasha Shur, Yoon Shin-Podskarbi, Bert L de Groot, Kathryn Miller, Jerry Vockley, Neal Sondheimer, Rebecca Ganetzky, Peter Freisinger	Pyruvate carboxylase deficiency type A and type C: Characterization of five novel pathogenic variants in PC and analysis of the genotype–phenotype correlation	Human mutation	10.1002/humu.23742	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/humu.23742
31	Eddy Elisée, Vytautas Gapsys, Nawel Mele, Ludovic Chaput, Edith Selwa, Bert L de Groot, Bogdan I Iorga	Performance evaluation of molecular docking and free energy calculations protocols using the D3R Grand Challenge 4 dataset	Journal of computer-aided molecular design	10.1007/s10822-019-00232-w	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10822-019-00232-w
32	M.F. Broekema, M.P.G. Massink, C. Donato, J. de Ligt, J. Schaarschmidt, M.G. Schooneman, F.S. van Nierop, D. Melchers, M.N. Gerding, R. Houtman, A.M.J.J. Bonvin, A.R. Majithia, H. Monajemi, G.W. van Haaften, M.R. Soeters and E. Kalkhoven.	Natural helix 9 mutants of PPAR γ differently affect its transcriptional activity	Molecular Metabolism	10.1016/j.molmet.2018.12.005	https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2212-8778(18)31027-5
33	C. Morris, P. Andreetto, L. Banci, A.M.J.J. Bonvin, G.G. Chojnowski, L. del Cano, J.M. Carazo, P. Conesa, S. Daenke, G. Damaskos, A. Giachetti, N. Haley, M. Hekkelman, P. Heuser, R. Joosten, D. Kouřil, A. Křenek, T. Kulhánek, V. Lamzin, N. Nadzirin, A. Perrakis, A. Rosato, F. Sanderson, J. Segura, J. Schaarschmidt, E. Sobolev, S. Traldi, M.E. Trellet, S. Velankar, M. Verlati, and M. Winn.	West-Life: A Virtual Research Environment for structural biology.	Journal of Structural Biology: X	10.1016/j.jsbx.2019.100006	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590152419300042
34	J.L. Roel Touris, A.M.J.J. Bonvin and B. Jimenez-Garcia	LightDock goes information-driven.	Bioinformatics	10.1093/bioinformatics/btz642	https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz642
35	R.A. Norman, F. Ambrosetti, A.M.J.J. Bonvin, L.J. Colwell,	Computational approaches to therapeutic antibody design:	Briefings in Bioinformatics	10.1093/bib/bbz095	https://academic.oup.com/bib/article-

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	S. Kelm, S. Kumar and K. Krawczyk	established methods and emerging trends.			lookup/doi/10.1093/bib/bbz095
36	J. Roel-Touris, C.G. Don, R.V. Honorato, J.P.G.L.M Rodrigues and A.M.J.J. Bonvin.	Less is more: Coarse-grained integrative modeling of large biomolecular assemblies with HADDOCK.	Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation	10.1021/acs.jctc.9b00310	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jctc.9b00310
37	R.V. Honorato, J. Roel-Touris and A.M.J.J. Bonvin	MARTINI-based protein-DNA coarse-grained HADDOCKing	Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences	10.3389/fmolb.2019.0102	https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmolb.2019.0102/full
38	M. Abraham, R. Apostolov, J. Barnoud, P. Bauer, C. Blau, A.M.J.J. Bonvin, M. Chavent, J. Chodera, K. Čondić-Jurkić, L. Delemotte, H. Grubmüller, R. Howard, E.J. Jordan, E. Lindal, O.H.S. Ollila, J. Selent, D. Smith, P. Stansfeld, J. Tiemann, M. Trellet, C. Woods and A. Zhmurov.	Sharing Data from Molecular Simulations	Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling	10.1021/acs.jcim.9b00665	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jcim.9b00665
39	H.M. Berman, P.D. Adams, A.M.J.J. Bonvin, S.K. Burley, B. Carragher, W. Chiu, F. DiMaio, T.E. Ferrin, M.J. Gabanyi, T.D. Goddard, P.R. Griffin, J. Haas, C.A. Hanke, J.C. Hoch, G. Hummer, G. Kurisu, C.L. Lawson, A. Leitner, J.L. Markley, J. Meiler, G.T. Montelione, G.N. Phillips Jr., T. Prisner, J. Rappsilber, D.C. Schriemer, T. Schwede, C.A.M. Seidel, T.S. Strutzenberg, D.I. Svergun, E. Tajkhorshid, J. Trewhella, B. Vallat, S. Velankar, G.W. Vuister, B. Webb, J.D. Westbrook, K.L. White, A. Sali.	Federating Structural Models and Data: Outcomes from A Workshop on Archiving Integrative Structures	Structure	10.1016/j.str.2019.11.002	https://www.cell.com/structure/fulltext/S0969-2126(19)30386-7?_returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2Fretrieve%2Fpii%2FS0969212619303867%3Fshowall%3Dtrue
40	M.F. Lensink, G. Brysbaert N. Nadzirin, S. Velankar, R.A.G. Chaleil, T. Gerguri, P.A. Bates, E. Laine, A. Carbone, S. Grudin, R. Kong, R. Liu, X. Xu, H. Shi, S. Chang, M. Eisenstein, A. Karczynska, C. Czaplewski, E. Lubecka, A. Lipska, P. Krupa, M. Mozolewska, L. Golon, S. Samsonov, A. Liwo, S. Crivelli, G. Pagès, M. Karasikov, M. Kadukova, Y. Yan, S. Huang, M. Rosell, L.A. Rodríguez-Lumbreras, M. Romero-Durana, L. Díaz-Bueno, J. Fernandez-Recio, C. Christoffer, G. Terashi, W. Shin, T. Aderinwale, S. Raghavendra Maddhuri Venkata Subraman, D. Kihara, D. Kozakov, S. Vajda, K. Porter, D. Padhorny, I.	Blind prediction of homo- and hetero-protein complexes: The CASP13-CAPRI experiment.	Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics	10.1002/prot.25838	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/prot.25838

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	<p>Desta, D. Beglov, M. Ignatov, S. Kotelnikov, I.H. Moal, D.W. Ritchie, I. Chauvot de Beauchêne, B. Maigret, M. Devignes, M.E. Ruiz Echartea, D. Barradas-Bautista, Z. Cao, L. Cavallo, R. Oliva, Y. Cao, Y. Shen, M. Baek, T. Park, H. Woo, C. Seok, M. Braitbard, L. Bitton, D. Scheidman-Duhovny, J. Dapkūnas, K. Olechnovič, Č. Venclovas, P.J. Kundrotas, S. Belkin, D. Chakravarty, V.D. Badal, I.A. Vakser, T.Vreven, S. Vangaveti, T. Borrman, Z. Weng, J.D. Guest, R. Gowthaman, B.G. Pierce, X. Xu, R. Duan, L. Qiu, J. Hou, B. Ryan Merideth, Z. Ma, J. Cheng, X. Zou, P.I. Koukos, J. Roel-Touris, . Ambrosetti, C. Geng. J. Schaarschmidt, M.E. Trellet, A.S.J. Melquiond, L. Xue, B. Jiménez-Garcí, C.W. van Noort, R.V. Honorato, A.M.J.J. Bonvin, S.J. Wodak</p>				
41	P.I. Koukos and A.M.J.J. Bonvin	Integrative modelling of biomolecular complexes.	Journal of Molecular Biology	10.1016/j.jmb.2019.11.009	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0022283619304516?via%3Dihub
42	F.Battistini, A. Hospital, D. Buitrago, D. Gallego, P.D.Dans, J.L. Gelpi and M.Orozco	How B-DNA Dynamics decipher sequence-selective protein recognition	Journal of Molecular Biology	10.1016/j.jmb.2019.07.021	
43	P.D.Dans, A.Balaceanu, M.Pasi, A.S.Patelli, D. Petkevičiūtė, J.Walther, A.Hospital, G.Bayarri, R.Lavery, J.H.Maddocks and M.Orozco	The static and Dynamic structural heterogeneities of B-DNA: extending Calladine-Dickerson rules	Nucleic Acids Research	10.1093/nar/gkz905	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6868377/
44	A.Hospital, F.Battistini, R.Soliva, J.L.Gelpí and M.Orozco	Surviving the Deluge of Biosimulation Data	Wires Computational Molecular Science	10.1002/wcms.1449	
45	D Gallego, L Darré, PD Dans and M Orozco	VeriNA3d: an R package for nucleic acids data mining	Bioinformatics	10.1093/bioinformatics/btz553	
46	A. Cuppari, P. Fernández-Millán, F. Battistini, A. Tarrés-Solé, S. Lyonnais, G. Iruela, E. Ruiz-Lopez, Y. Enciso, A. Rubio-Cosials, R. Prohens, M. Pons, C. Alfonso, K. Tóth, G. Rivas, M. Orozco, M. Solà	DNA specificities modulate the binding of human transcription factor A to mitochondrial DNA control region	Nucleic Acids Research	10.1093/nar/gkz406	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6614842/?report=classic

Table 3. 2019 Publication list

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No	Authors	Title	Journal	DOI	Open Access Link
1	G. Groenhof, V. Modi, D. Morozov	Observe while it happens: catching photoactive proteins in the act with non-adiabatic molecular dynamics simulations	Curr. Opin. Struct. Biol.	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbi.2019.12.013	https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S0959440X19301526?token=CBB685FE8558FAB4EEEE511D64E2DC34FF9ADD492A6135E0FCB693A54ECA8E2F40BD12650998A248B7415831863C4CA4
2	S. Mustalahti, D. Morozov, H. L. Luk, R. R. Pallerla, P. Myllyperkiö, M. Pettersson, P. Pihko, G. Groenhof	Photoactive Yellow Protein Chromophore Photoisomerizes around a Single Bond if the Double Bond is Locked	J. Phys. Chem. Lett.	https://dx.doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.0c00060	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.0c00060
3	E. Claesson, W. Y. Wahlgren, H. Takala, S. Pandey, L. Castillon, V. Kuznetsova, L. Henry, M. Panman, M. Carrillo, J. Kuebel, R. Nanekar, L. Isaksson, A. Nimmrich, A. Cellini, D. Morozov, M. Maj, M. Kurttila, R. Bosman, E. Nango, R. Tanaka, T. Tanaka, L. Fangjia, S. Iwata, S. Owada, K. Moffat, G. Groenhof, E. A. Stojkovic, J. A. Ihalainen, M. Schmidt, S. Westenhoff	The primary structural photoresponse of phytochrome proteins captured by a femtosecond X-ray laser	eLife	10.7554/eLife.53514	https://elifesciences.org/articles/53514
4	Tsourtou, Flora; Peristeras, Loukas; Apostolov, Rossen; Mavrantzas, Vlasis	Molecular dynamics simulation of amorphous poly(3-hexylthiophene)	Macromolecules	In review	In review
5	M.G. Chiariello V. Bolnykh, E. Ippoliti, S. Meloni, J. M. Hugaard Olsen, T. Beck, U. Rothlisberger, C. Fahlke and P. Carloni	Molecular Basis of CLC Antiporter Inhibition by Fluoride	Journal of the American Chemical Society	10.1021/jacs.9b13588	https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/jacs.9b13588
6	V. Bolnykh J. M. Hugaard Olsen, S. Meloni, M. P. Bircher, E. Ippoliti, P. Carloni and U. Rothlisberger	MiMiC: Multiscale Modeling in Computational Chemistry	Frontiers in Molecular Biosciences	10.3389/fmolb.2020.00045	https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmolb.2020.00045/full
7	Vytautas Gapsys, Laura Pérez-Benito, Matteo	Large scale relative protein ligand	Chemical Science	10.1039/c9sc03754c	https://pubs.rsc.org/en/content/articlepdf/2020

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	Aldeghi, Daniel Seeliger, Herman van Vlijmen, Gary Tresadern, Bert L de Groot	binding affinities using non-equilibrium alchemy			0/sc/c9sc03754c
8	Andrea Rizzi, Travis Jensen, David R Slochower, Matteo Aldeghi, Vytautas Gapsys, Dimitris Ntekoumes, Stefano Bosisio, Michail Papadourakis, Niel M Henriksen, Bert L De Groot, Zoe Cournia, Alex Dickson, Julien Michel, Michael K Gilson, Michael R Shirts, David L Mobley, John D Chodera	The SAMPL6 SAMPLing challenge: Assessing the reliability and efficiency of binding free energy calculations	Journal of Computer-Aided Molecular Design	10.1007/s10822-020-00290-5	https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007/s10822-020-00290-5.pdf
9	M.E. Trellet, G. van Zundert and A.M.J.J. Bonvin.	Protein–Protein Modeling Using Cryo-EM Restraints	Methods in Molecular Biology	10.1007/978-1-0716-0270-6_11	http://arxiv.org/abs/2005.00435
10	J.L. Roel Touris, A.M.J.J. Bonvin and B. Jimenez-Garcia	LightDock goes information-driven.	Bioinformatics	10.1093/bioinformatics/btz642	https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btz642
11	F. Ambrosetti, B. Jiménez-García, J. Roel-Touris and A.M.J.J. Bonvin.	Modeling Antibody-Antigen Complexes by Information-Driven Docking	Structure	10.1016/j.str.2019.10.011	https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3362436
12	A. Basciu, P.I. Koukos, G. Malloci, A.M.J.J. Bonvin and A.V. Vargiu	Coupling enhanced sampling of the apo-receptor with template-based ligand conformers selection: performance in pose prediction in the D3R Grand Challenge 4.	Journal of Computer-Aided Molecular Design	10.1007/s10822-019-00244-6	http://arxiv.org/abs/2005.04142
13	Z. Kurkcuoglu and A.M.J.J. Bonvin	Pre- and post-docking sampling of conformational changes using ClustENM and HADDOCK for protein-protein and protein-DNA systems	Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics	10.1002/prot.25802	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/prot.25802
14	P.I. Koukos, J. Roel-Touris, F. Ambrosetti, C. Geng, J. Schaarschmidt, M.E. Trellet, A.S.J. Melquiond, L.C. Xue, R.V. Honorato, I. Moreira, Z. Kurkcuoglu, A. Vangone and A.M.J.J. Bonvin.	An overview of data-driven HADDOCK strategies in CAPRI rounds 38-45.	Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics	10.1002/prot.25869	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/prot.25869
15	F. Ambrosetti, T.H. Olsed,	proABC-2:	bioRxiv	10.1101/20	https://www.biorxiv.org

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	P.P. Olimpieri, B. Jiménez-García, E. Milanetti, P. Marcatilli and A.M.J.J. Bonvin	PRediction Of AntiBody Contacts v2 and its application to information-driven docking		20.03.18.967828	/content/10.1101/2020.03.18.967828v1.full
16	C. Orengo, S. Velankar, S. Wodak, V. Zoete, A.M.J.J. Bonvin, A. Elofsson, K.A. Feenstra, D.L. Gerloff, T. Hamelryck, J.M. Hancock, M. Helmer-Citterich, A. Hospital, M. Orozco, A. Perrakis, M. Rarey, C. Soares, J.L. Sussman, J.M. Thornton, P. Tuffery, G. Tusnady, R. Wierenga, T. Salminen, B. Schneider	A community proposal to integrate structural bioinformatics activities in ELIXIR (3D-Bioinfo Community) [version 1; peer review: awaiting peer review].	F1000 Research	10.12688/f1000research.20559.1	https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.20559.1
17	R. Shukla, J. Medeiros-Silva, A. Parmar, B.J.A. Vermeulen, S. Das, A. Paioni, S. Jekhmane, J. Lorent, A.M.J.J. Bonvin, M. Baldus, M. Lelli, E.J.A. Veldhuizen, E. Breukink, I. Singh and M. Weingarth	Mode of action of teixobactins in cellular conditions	Nature Communication	10.1038/s41467-020-16600-2	https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-020-16600-2
18	F. Ambrosetti, Zuzana Jandova and A.M.J.J. Bonvin	A protocol for information-driven antibody-antigen modelling with the HADDOCK2.4 webserver	ArXiv,		https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.03283

Table 4. 2020 Publication list

2.7 Conclusion about reach/impact

With the growth of our social media following, we have been able to expand our reach virtually while also increasing attendance at events by promoting them online. Using digital media, we can communicate the value of our research publications to a broader audience.

2.8 Future strategy

In the hope to better understand our social media audience we aim to, in collaboration with WP3, conduct a social network analysis in Q3/Q4 of 2020. Twitter removed the audience analytics page in January 2020, and we have therefore lost information such as geographic location, gender, age and interests of our Twitter audience. These measures were relatively crude, but it has sparked discussion about replacement tools. A deeper network analysis of relevant hashtags, words and users, using software such as Socioviz (<https://socioviz.net/>)

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or similar, may allow us to understand which communities we are reaching more optimally than others and how to adjust our strategy accordingly.

To maintain consistent branding, social media templates will be designed to be used during event and webinar promotion. New content formats such as polls will be trialed on twitter to improve audience engagement.

3. Training

Here we present the training events carried out after December 2019, as the previous events with participation from BioExcel were reported in deliverable D4.2. - *Training plan*. We include information about contents, participation and feedback. We present additional results from training impact assessment, including information collected in the last six months.

In addition, the BioExcel training programme builds on the strong commitment the BioExcel partners have to deliver high quality training to the computational biomolecular community. Additional courses in which BioExcel partners have delivered training are presented in table 2 in section 2.5 (*Dissemination and training events*) of this deliverable.

We present an updated plan of training events for the rest of the project. Additional events will be added to the BioExcel training programme when they are confirmed.

3. Events originally planned as face-to-face events

In the period between January 2020 and June 2020, BioExcel has organised 1 event. The COVID-19 pandemic has affected the events planned in these months: the EMBO practical course has been postponed until November and the BioExcel Summer School has been delivered as a virtual event. Details about how we organised this are presented below. We will report on how the BioExcel Summer School went in the next deliverable.

3.1.1 EMBO Practical Course Integrative modelling of biomolecular interactions Izmir (Turkey) - sponsored by BioExcel.

This course was planned to happen in May, but because of the COVID-19 pandemic, it has been postponed to November 2020:

<https://meetings.embo.org/event/20-biomolecular-interactions>

3.1.2 Remote BioExcel Summer School in Biomolecular Simulations

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, we are running the Summer School as a remote event (<https://bioexcel.eu/events/bioexcel-summer-school-on-biomolecular-simulations-2020/>) between June 22 and June 26. The announcement that we

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would convert the BioExcel Summer School into a remote event got an excellent response from the community, with many people interested in the event. Almost 180 people registered online, 85 of which sent all the required documents. From those, we selected 30 participants to take part in the remote course. Parts of the Summer School will be made available on our YouTube channel.

The topics included in the course are molecular dynamics simulations, biomolecular docking, BioExcel building blocks (Biobb), QM/MM, Free energy calculations and advanced sampling methods (metadynamics). Based on the feedback received after the 2019 edition, we have included a more comprehensive introduction to molecular dynamics simulations, simplified the GROMACS tutorial, and added more time for questions after the CP2K session. In addition, the programme includes three short talks from trainers to show how the BioExcel software is used in their research.

The summer school is intended for researchers (primarily PhD and postdocs) using or planning to use biomolecular modeling and simulations in their everyday research. Familiarity with Linux and some basic knowledge of molecular modelling software is a requirement.

The remote summer school includes a combination of pre-recorded lectures, live Q&A sessions and live hands-on sessions. Participants have also the possibility of asking questions through the ask.bioexcel forum, which was also used as a channel for social interaction. For the hands-on sessions, we provide virtual machines for the participants, with all the software required already installed. During the hands-on computer practicals students will use, among others, the BioExcel flagship software (GROMACS, HADDOCK, PMX and CP2K). The poster session is organised as a combination of 1-minute presentation by the participants and discussions in the forum about the posters, which are available online during the whole course.

As the Summer School is in the end of June 2020, it is out of the scope of this deliverable to assess it. We will report on the event and the results of the feedback survey in the next training deliverable.

3.2 Remote training programme

After the success of the pilot courses that we ran in 2019, we decided to incorporate remote training courses to the BioExcel training programme. In deliverable D4.2. - *Training plan*, we included some planned courses. All of them have been delivered, although not always in the initially planned dates. In total, since January 2020, we have run 5 remote courses and an internal training session for the Summer School trainers:

- *Using Twitter to promote your project*. Run twice: 31 January 2020 and 3 April 2020.
- *ResOps: Cloud-native tools and technology for researchers*. 24 to 28 February 2020.

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- *Reproducible analyses with Common Workflow Language*. 29 April 2020.
- *Preparing your systems for running QM/MM simulations in CP2K with AmberTools*. 9 June 2020.
- *Using GoToTraining and Panopto*. 7 and 14 May 2020

Below, we describe each course including the content, structure and feedback received.

3.2.1 Using Twitter to promote your project

This course introduced the inner workings of Twitter and discussed how to create content in Twitter and how to increase the visibility of your posts. It also covered Twitter analytics, Twitter best practice and how Twitter is best used when you are using it as part of a team. The trainers were Vera Matser and Michelle Mendonca, from EMBL-EBI.

This course has been delivered twice in the last 6 months (January, April and May). It was delivered as a single 3 h online session through GoToTraining. It consisted of a combination of lecturing by two trainers and activities where participants worked on a document shared through GoToTraining, both individually and in groups. During the whole session, participants could ask questions and discuss with the trainers.

These sessions were half an hour longer than when the course was delivered in October. We extended the session as a result of the feedback received then, because there was not enough time for the second activity. With the longer session, there was enough time to complete the two hands-on activities. Also, in response to previous feedback, the documents for the activities were more structured, so that it was clearer for participants what to do.

Most people who registered attended the sessions (85%). Most participants (73%) completed the feedback survey. The general satisfaction in the two sessions was very high, most of them (87%) rated the course as 4 or 5, in a scale where 5 was the maximum score. All respondents would recommend the course. Among the best of the course, they mention: useful tips, hands-on activities, good overview, possibility to ask questions. Among the worst, they mentioned that the session is too long and could have a break and that there were some technical issues. This is a consequence of the longer duration of the course, for next editions, we will introduce a break. The session in April was the first one where nobody had problems accessing the activities presented in breakout rooms. On the other hand, there were more sound problems from the trainers, probably because they were at home due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

3.2.2 ResOps: Cloud-native tools and technology for researchers

This course covered basic tools and technologies needed to succeed in the cloud, with hands-on exercises. It provided some background to cloud computing and practical experience in building, deploying and running applications in cloud

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platforms – Embassy (OpenStack), Google, Amazon and Azure. The course contents included building Docker containers, deploying applications in Kubernetes and using GitLab for continuous integration and deployment. The course agenda and material can be found at <https://bit.ly/resops-bioexcel>. The trainers were Tony Wildish, David Yuan and C.D. Tiwari, from EMBL-EBI.

This course consisted of four sessions with a duration of 3 hours that combined presentations by the trainers and hands-on exercises where participants worked on their own with the possibility of receiving support from the trainers if needed. The sessions were delivered with GoToTraining. Participants were given access to virtual machines in the cloud, where they could work for 2 weeks after the course ended.

Out of 35 people registered, 24 attended the first session, 19 the second one, 15 the third one and 10 the last session. The materials provided through the link above allowed people to follow the course on their own in an asynchronous manner, so we do not know whether the people who did not attend the last sessions completed the course on their own. Participants who joined the sessions were active in asking questions both through the chat and using their microphone.

Five people responded to the course feedback survey and they all rated the course with a score of 4 or 5, where 5 is best. Each of them replied differently to the question *What was the best part of the course?* Responses include: practicals, materials, lectures, Kubernetes, the possibility of using the virtual machines. None of them pointed to anything as the worst part of the course. 4 of them would recommend the course and the last one replied *maybe* to that question.

3.2.3 Reproducible analyses with Common Workflow Language

This course provided a brief introduction to the Common Workflow Language (CWL) and helped participants get started with the CWL reference implementation cwltool, as well as giving them a taster of the implementation Toil (an open-source pure-Python workflow engine) using the BioExcel Cloud Portal. It also included best practice guidelines for writing CWL and how to share and reuse workflow and tool descriptions with the CWL community. The trainers were Stian Soiland-Reyes and Robin Long, from The University of Manchester (a partner in BioExcel), and Michael Crusoe, from the CWL project.

The course was delivered through GoToTraining in a session that lasted two and a half hours. It combined presentations from the trainer with hands-on tutorials that the participants followed in virtual machines provided through the BioExcel Cloud Portal. Because of this, we initially limited the course to 20 participants, but in the end allowed 24 to register.

15 people attended the session. 7 of them completed the feedback survey and all of them rated the course with a score of 4 or 5, where 5 is best. Most of them said that the best part of the course was the hands-on tutorial, while 2 of them mentioned the thorough explanation in the first hour as the best. Regarding the

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worst of the course, 2 respondents mentioned the Visual Studio Code setup, one the lack of time for the hands-on and another one that there were too few practicals. The rest of respondents did not reply to this question. We will work on improving the setup instructions and the time and amount of exercises for future editions of the course. All respondents would recommend the course.

3.2.4 Preparing your systems for running QM/MM simulations in CP2K with AmberTools

This course covered basic tools and technologies needed to succeed in setting up a QM/MM simulation with AmberTools suite. It provided background to preparation of biological systems for molecular modelling and practical experience in successfully creating topologies and running simple QM/MM simulations using CP2K in a HPC environment. It was aimed at biomolecular modellers who want to use QM/MM simulations in their work. The trainers were Arno Proeme, Julien Sindt, Holly Judge and Salomé Llabrés Prats, from EPCC (UEDIN, a partner in BioExcel). The course is the first of a series entitled *Roadmap to run your QM/MM simulations using CP2K and GROMACS*.

It ran as a 3 hours online session delivered through BlackBoard Collaborate with a combination of lectures and hands-on exercises. Participants had access to ARCHER2 (a supercomputer at the UK National Supercomputing service) for the hands-on and they were able to access it until the end of the week.

30 people registered for the course and 13 joined the session. From these, 5 responded to the feedback survey. Three of them rated the course with the maximum score (5) and the other 2 rated it with a score of 3. Four respondents would recommend the course and the other one did not reply to this question. The best of the course, according to them, was that it was possible for beginners to follow. Regarding the worst of the course, they mentioned lack of some explanations and technical issues accessing Archer. We will discuss with the trainers whether to add more detailed explanations in this session or leave them for the other sessions in the series and make clearer in the course description what is covered in each session.

3.2.5 Using GoToTraining and Panopto

In addition to the previous courses, we organised an internal training session about how to use GoToTraining and Panopto for the trainers of the BioExcel Summer School. This session described the main functions of the GoToTraining control panel and explained how to record and edit videos in Panopto, the tool used for creating the pre-recorded lectures for the Summer School. This session was delivered twice to give all trainers the possibility to attend. It was delivered by Marta Lloret Llinares (EMBL-EBI) through GoToTraining.

3.3 Impact assessment

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To ensure the quality of the training programme BioExcel routinely collects course feedback for all BioExcel training activities. The responses provide us with valuable information on how to improve our events and the direction of the training programme. However, these responses are generally collected on the last day of the event and therefore do not provide us with a lot of information about the long-term impact of the BioExcel training programme and tend to focus on immediate concerns (e.g. a problem with a tutorial, a session was too short or too difficult). To assess the impact of our training programme activities, we want to know if attending our training courses has had a positive impact on their research/career and whether or not they are actively using the tools that were introduced to them during the training event.

To assess the long-term impact, BioExcel sends two long-term feedback surveys to all delegates who have attended BioExcel training courses, the first one is sent approximately 6-12 months after the training event, the second survey is sent after 2 years. The surveys collect data on whether participants are using the tools they were introduced to during the training course, whether they have established collaborations, and whether they have taught others. In addition, we ask what impact the course has had on their research and the research of others, as well as what the best and worst parts of the course was.

Since the last deliverable (D4.2. - *Training plan*), we have collected long-term feedback data from some of the courses delivered in 2019. We sent the long-term feedback survey (6-12 months after the course) to the participants of the Seasonal School 2019 and of the BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations 2019.

The response rate was as follows:

Course	Number of participants who received the survey	Response rate
2019 Seasonal School	53	19%
2019 Summer School	27	48%

Table 5. Response rate to long-term feedback surveys

3.3.1 Long-term feedback survey 6-12 months

Here we present the results of the survey analysing collectively the responses from all participants who replied to it.

Many BioExcel training events teach participants how to use certain computational tools, so a direct impact that we can have is that they actively use these tools in their research. All respondents said they have applied the tools they learned about in their own research and indicated which ones they have used, as shown in Fig. 10 (note that they could provide more than one answer).

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Figure 10. Percentage of respondents choosing the indicated answers to the question “During your course you will have learnt and used a variety of methods and resources. Since the course, have you applied the following in your own research?”

One way in which our courses have an impact in the research community is that the participants share what they learned with colleagues and students. Most respondents (74%) have taught someone (Fig. 11). This means that our training reaches more people than the ones who attend our courses.

Figure 11. Percentage of respondents choosing the indicated answers to the question “How many others have you taught the skills and/or knowledge that you learnt during the course this year?”

Our training courses also promote networking, as they include time for participants to interact with each other and with the trainers during breaks and social activities. These interactions might lead to collaborations that will directly impact the research activities of the participants. In our long-term feedback survey we asked “Did you establish any collaborations with other participants / BioExcel researchers during this course?” 47% of respondents replied positively to that question.

We also ask our former participants if they would recommend our course, or if they have already recommended it. All respondents to this survey would recommend the course they attended and 67% of them have already recommended it to someone else. This speaks extremely well about the positive experience that they had during the BioExcel courses.

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In addition to a number of pre-formulated questions, we also include the following in our survey: “Please comment on the impact that the course has had on your research and the research of others”. To analyse the impact statements we try to find common themes across the responses. We score each statement across the commonly identified themes. As we saw that they matched the results we obtained this time, we used the same themes as in deliverable [“D4.6 - Final report on dissemination and training”](#) - of the previous funding phase of BioExcel. Not all the themes in the list were matched by responses to the present survey.

Some participant statements contain more than one theme. The most commonly reported themes are “Gaining knowledge/skills” with 11 counts and “Essential to research/actively using skills” with 6 counts (Fig. 12). These two related themes indicate that our training is successful in transmitting participants important skills for their research. Following this, participants also indicated that they “expanded their network” or that the course “encouraged further learning. In addition to this, participants reported “I taught others” and “published a paper” as outcomes from the course.

Figure 12. Analysis of the impact statements collected in the 6-12 months long-term feedback survey. Number of statements from participants that match the indicated themes.

3.3.2 Conclusion long-term feedback

It is difficult to quantify the long-term feedback of training activities. The best that we can do is to assess whether participants use the skills they learned during the courses, whether they passed these skills to others and whether the course contributed to the outcome of their research. The response rate to our long-term feedback surveys is not high, especially for the Seasonal School, but this is usual for this type of survey. At EMBL-EBI, where they have collected long-term feedback since 2010, the response rate is around 25%, so the response rates that we obtain is comparable to that or clearly better in the case of the Summer School (48%).

We are pleased that, from the responses we get, participants consider that they gained knowledge and skills from the course and many of them use the skills

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acquired in their research. In addition, it is clear that our training programme reaches more people than the course delegates, as many of them teach others afterwards. We will continue collecting long-term feedback from past and future training events to monitor the impact that we have in the community.

3.4 Competency mapper development and reference profiles

The BioExcel Training programme is based on a competency profile. This allows us to define the competencies that users of BioExcel need to develop to enable them to fully exploit the applications and services provided by BioExcel. Version 2 of the BioExcel competency profile was reported in deliverable D4.2 - *Training plan* and is available on the BioExcel Knowledge Resource Centre (<http://krc.bioexcel.eu/competencies>) and the competency mapper site at EBI (<https://competency.ebi.ac.uk/framework/bioexcel/2.0>).

We are extending the competency mapper tool towards the area of [career development](#) (Fig. 13). We can now create reference profiles, e.g. research software engineer, computational chemist, system administrator in an HPC centre, which are rated against the BioExcel competency profile. One of these profiles is now public on the website ([junior software research engineer](#)) and we are working to make the others available soon.

It is possible to compare two profiles and see which competencies are different between the two (Fig. 14). Users will also be able to create their own profile and rate it to the competencies for self-assessment and professional development purposes. They will be able to compare that profile to the reference profiles included in the tool, which can inform their career development. In future, we will add learning pathways with curated sets of training resources to achieve specific development goals.

Figure 13. Screenshot of the front page of the career development site

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Figure 14. Screenshot showing part of the comparison between two reference profiles, junior research software engineer and system administrator for HPC.

3.5 Future plans

Several activities are already planned for the rest of the BioExcel project. They are listed below in two sections, depending on whether they are face-to-face or remote courses. If the current pandemic continues to affect the planned events, we will consider whether to deliver them in an online format. The experience gained through our remote training courses since 2019 places us in an excellent position to provide high quality training in this format.

In addition, bespoke training for industry is coordinated by the industry liaison (WP5) in collaboration with the in-depth support activities (WP3). Virtual training is planned with AstraZeneca and training and support with advanced free energy calculations using GROMACS/pmx with a SME providing virtual hit-to-lead services. (See D3.4 - *User Community Support and Engagement Report (half-time update)* for more detail)

Other training activities with BioExcel participation will be added to our programme as soon as they are confirmed.

Face-to-face

- EMBO Practical Course *Integrative modelling of biomolecular interactions*, 2-6 November 2020, Izmir (Turkey) - sponsored by BioExcel. <http://meetings.embo.org/event/20-biomolecular-interactions>
- Training tutorials (topics to be confirmed) during the EMBO Workshop *Advances and Challenges in Biomolecular Simulations*, 17-20 October 2021, Brno (Czech Republic).
- Hands-on introduction to HPC for Life Scientists. This course will be organised jointly with PRACE in the first quarter of 2021.
- BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations 2021.

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- CCP-BioSim & BioExcel training around QM/MM 2021
- We plan to organise a new training event together with the new PerMed CoE when it starts its activities.

Remote training programme

We will continue delivering remote training courses, as we have done since autumn 2019 with excellent results. Here we list the ones that are already planned. We will add other courses to the remote training programme as soon as they are confirmed.

- Series of courses *Roadmap to run your QM/MM simulations using CP2K and GROMACS*, organised jointly with ARCHER
 - Session 1: *Preparing your systems for running QM/MM simulations in CP2K with AmberTools*, run in June 2020 and already reported here.
 - Session 2: *MD simulation setup using GROMACS tools*, 3rd quarter in 2020.
 - Session 3: *Performing MD simulations using GROMACS tools*, 3rd quarter in 2020.
 - Session 4: *Performing GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM simulation*, 4th quarter in 2020.
- *Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel building blocks*, 4th quarter in 2020.

4. Conclusion

In the light of the COVID-19 crisis, launching the COVID-19 research page on our website allows us to showcase our research and collaborations with international initiatives such as Molecular Sciences Software Institute and EOSC-Life to name a few. Through our dissemination strategy, we can leverage our digital marketing channels to communicate the value of our research on SARS-CoV-2. In addition, by engaging with FocusCoE on Twitter, LinkedIn and newsletters, we can promote our events, webinars and research, thus expanding our reach to bring in new audiences.

BioExcel is involved in training by directly organising (or co-organising) events, and delivering training on other events through BioExcel partners. The training programme incorporated remote courses after the success of the pilot courses in 2019. This allowed us to deliver high quality training in 2020, even if we had to postpone face-to-face events or convert the BioExcel Summer School into an online event due to COVID-19. The experience gained through the remote courses helped us organise this event. Running the Summer School remotely will teach us extremely valuable lessons for the future of our training programme, as we will learn both from the experience itself and from the feedback received after the course.

The BioExcel training programme includes events that are organised in partnership with other initiatives, such as PRACE or ARCHER. These

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collaborations extend now to remote courses, e.g. the series *Roadmap to run your QM/MM simulations using CP2K and GROMACS*, starting in June 2020. We expect to maintain these collaborations and start new ones during the rest of the project, for example: we envision working with the new PerMed CoE in organising training events.

During the rest of the project, BioExcel will continue to reach out to the computational biomolecular community and to deliver high quality training.